

ANALYSIS OF THE RANGE OF MEDICINES USED IN THE TREATMENT OF DISEASES OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the study, the assortment of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system was studied according to the registration indicators using issues 23-27 of 2019 – 2023 of the "State Register of Drugs, Medical Products and Medical Equipment Allowed for Use in Medical Practice". According to the results of the analysis, in 2019, 216 assortment of trade name drugs used in diseases of the gastrointestinal system in the country were recorded by domestic manufacturers, 110 – from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, and 305 – by foreign manufacturers. In 2023, there were 202, 100, 438 medicines, respectively. In 2019 – 2023, the range of drugs produced by foreign countries with international unpatented names in 38 pharmacological groups increased by 31.5 %, the range of drugs produced by local pharmaceutical enterprises increased by 11.42 %, drugs produced by the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States decreased by 4.29 %.*

Keywords: *medicines, assortment, international nonproprietary name, registration indicator, pharmacotherapeutic groups, update index.*

Introduction. According to the report of the World Health Organization, in 2015, gastrointestinal tract diseases are the second most common after respiratory diseases. Diseases of the gastrointestinal system make up about 10% of all diseases [1]. Human digestion is a complex process in which large insoluble food molecules are broken down into smaller water-soluble food molecules. The soluble food molecules then pass into the small intestine where nutrients are absorbed and from there into the blood circulation system to different parts of the body. The main purpose of digestion is to continuously provide energy for processes such as growth, development, differentiation and other functions of the body, such as regeneration, reproduction, lactation [2].

Today, diseases of the gastrointestinal system are widespread, accounting for 8% of all diseases worldwide. These diseases are characterized by the processes of physiological regeneration of the stomach and intestinal mucosa and their motor functions, as well as pancreatic enzyme deficiency, etc. Bad habits such as poor diet, stress, drinking and smoking, as well as living in environmentally unfavorable areas influence the occurrence of these diseases [3].

Diseases of the gastrointestinal tract include diseases of the esophagus, stomach, small intestine, colon, and rectum. Common gastrointestinal symptoms include recurrent abdominal pain, abdominal bloating, nausea, indigestion, dyspepsia, vomiting, diarrhea, and constipation. Gastrointestinal diseases are one of the most common diseases, the most common of which are esophageal diseases and dysphagia, peptic ulcer, gastroparesis or chronic gastric motor dysfunction, irritable bowel syndrome, and inflammatory bowel disease [4]. Due to the increasing

number of patients with gastrointestinal tract and hepatobiliary system diseases worldwide every year, early diagnosis of these diseases remains one of the priority medical and social tasks today. Because diseases are not treated in time, they often turn into more severe, chronic and incurable forms. Therefore, when pathological processes occur in different parts of the digestive tract, it is important to assess and diagnose the general laws of their structural and functional restoration [5].

Disruption of the secretory and motor functions of the gastrointestinal tract is observed in many diseases and pathological conditions. In order to normalize the functioning of the body, a large assortment of drugs used in the treatment of the gastrointestinal tract is used. They mainly contain substances that directly affect the secretory and motor functions of the stomach and intestines, as well as the excretory functions of the pancreas and liver. At the same time, they also include appetite stimulants and antiemetics [6]. The above-mentioned problems justify the necessity and relevance of studying, analyzing the index and range of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system.

Methods. International unpatented list of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system using issues 23-27 of 2019-2023 of the "State register of drugs, medical products and medical equipment approved for use in medical practice". [7, 8, 9, 10, 11] The statistical method of comparative analysis of the range of medicines by name and trade names was used.

Results and discussions. During the study of the structure of the assortment of medicines, the indicators of registration with trade names of medicines used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system were analyzed by year.

Figure 1 shows the change in the registration rate in 2019-2023 more clearly. The highest number of registrations for drugs produced by foreign countries was 471 in 2022 and 438 in 2023.

Figure 1. Analysis of drugs by producing countries

Indicators of registration of drugs produced by domestic manufacturers in 2019 are 216 medicines, in 2020 - 238 medicines. From the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, 113 drugs were registered in 2020, 115 drugs – in 2022.

Table 1.

Registration indicators by drug manufacturers, in percent

№	Drug producing countries	Years				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Domestic manufacturers	34,2	31,94	29,2	26,9	27,3
2	Manufacturers of countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	17,4	15,16	15,17	14,3	13,5
3	Foreign manufacturers	48,4	52,9	55,63	58,8	59,2
4	Total percent	100	100	100	100	100

According to Table 1, the registration rates by manufacturers of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system increased by 17.27% in 5 years.

The share of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system registered in state registers in 2019-2023 was taken by drugs manufactured by foreign countries (48.4-59.2%). Medicines produced by local manufacturers (34.2 - 27.3%) and finally medicines produced by the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (17.4 - 13.5%) took the second place.

Table 2.

Indicators of registration of drugs produced by foreign countries

№	Countries	Years				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Austria	5	3	2	2	2
2	Bangladesh	1	1	1	4	5
3	Belgium	1	–	–	–	–
4	Bulgaria	11	12	11	9	7
5	Great Britain	2	2	1	1	1
6	Hungary	1	2	2	3	3
7	Vietnam	–	1	1	2	2
8	Germany	20	29	25	23	23
9	Greece	3	4	5	5	4
10	Egypt	2	3	1	–	–
11	India	141	176	182	253	230
12	Indonesia	1	1	1	1	–
13	Jordan	1	1	1	–	–
14	Iran	6	5	5	2	2
15	Spain	1	3	2	5	5
16	Italy	15	20	19	18	17
17	Canada	2	–	1	–	–
18	China	4	13	13	14	14
19	Korea	1	6	6	7	6
20	Latvia	1	2	2	1	1
21	The Netherlands	4	3	2	2	2
22	United Arab Emirates	1	–	–	1	1

23	Pakistan	11	18	17	27	27
24	Poland	7	7	6	5	5
25	Portugal	4	2	2	2	2
26	Republic of Macedonia	1	1	1	–	–
27	Romania	2	5	3	6	6
28	Slovenia	14	13	13	14	12
29	Turkey	19	32	31	33	35
30	France	16	15	17	17	13
31	Republic of Montenegro	1	1	–	–	–
32	Czech Republic	3	6	6	5	4
33	Switzerland	2	1	–	–	–
34	Japan	1	3	3	4	4
35	Argentina	–	1	1	1	1
36	Ireland	–	1	1	1	1
37	Thailand	–	1	1	2	2
38	Sweden	–	–	–	1	1
	Total number	305	394	385	471	438

Table 2 shows the registration indicators by trade name from 38 foreign countries, according to which, in 2019, 305 drugs used in the treatment of gastrointestinal system diseases were registered, and in 2023, 438 drugs used in the treatment of gastrointestinal system diseases were registered, with a growth rate of 43.6% in 5 years.

Indications of registration of drugs used in the treatment of gastrointestinal diseases from 38 foreign countries are given, in which India registered 141 drugs in 2019 and 253 drugs in 2023, accounting for 46.23% in 2019 and 53.7% in 2022. , Turkey - 19 drugs in 2019, 35 drugs in 2023, 6.23% in 2019 and 8% in 2023 and Germany - 20 drugs in 2019, 29 drugs in 2023, 6.55% in 2019 and 7% in 2020 , 36% of the registration share, occupying the leading positions.

Table 3.

Indicators of registration of drugs produced by the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States

№	Countries	Years				
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1	Republic of Armenia	1	1	–	–	–
2	Republic of Belarus	13	13	14	15	10
3	Georgia	13	15	11	13	12
4	Republic of Kazakhstan	1	2	2	1	1
5	Moldova	3	3	2	2	2
6	Russian Federation	44	45	40	46	44
7	Ukraine	35	34	36	38	31
	Total number	110	113	105	115	100

Table 3 shows the registration indicators by trade name from 7 countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, according to which, in 2019, 110 drugs used in the

treatment of gastrointestinal system diseases were registered, and in 2023, 100 drugs used in the treatment of gastrointestinal system diseases were registered, which is 9.1% in 5 years.

Among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, the Russian Federation recorded 44 drugs in 2019 and 44 in 2023. The registration rate was 38% in 2021 and 44% in 2023, Ukraine was registered 35 medicines in 2019 and 31 in 2023. The registration rate was 30% in 2019 and 33% in 2023, and the Republic of Belarus took the leading positions with 13 drugs registered in 2019, 10 in 2023, 10% in 2019 and 13.3% in 2021.

Table 4.

Analysis by pharmacological group and international non-proprietary name

№	Name of pharmacological groups	Years														
		2019			2020			2021			2022			2023		
		Number of drugs by international non-proprietary name														
Foreign countries	Countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	Domestic manufacturers	Foreign countries	Countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	Domestic manufacturers	Foreign countries	Countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	Domestic manufacturers	Foreign countries	Countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	Domestic manufacturers	Foreign countries	Countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States	Domestic manufacturers		
1	Antacid drugs	1	1	-	3	1	-	2	1	-	1	1	-	3	1	-
2	Enzymes and enzyme drugs	6	5	3	5	2	2	2	1	1	3	1	1	3	1	1
3	Anti-enzyme drugs	-	-	-	-	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Anti-emetic drugs	7	3	1	8	3	2	9	3	5	10	3	5	9	3	5
5	Laxative drugs	15	6	12	14	3	13	15	4	15	15	5	12	13	5	12
6	Antidiarrheal drugs	9	2	4	10	2	4	10	2	2	11	2	2	10	2	2
7	Drugs against flatulence	10	1	3	12	1	3	11	2	5	10	3	5	10	3	5
8	Carminative drugs	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-
9	Anti-ulcer drugs	17	4	3	17	4	3	17	5	3	20	7	2	20	7	2
10	Anti-ulcer drugs (H2-blocker)	3	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	3	4	-	4	4	-	4
11	Anti-ulcer drugs (Antacid)	18	1	3	21	1	4	21	2	6	19	2	6	15	2	6
12	Anti-ulcer drugs (astringent and enveloping drugs)	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
13	Anti-ulcer drugs (Proton pump inhibitors)	8	2	3	9	2	4	12	3	7	14	3	9	15	3	8
14	Anti-ulcer drugs (rabepazole in combination with other drugs)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
15	Drugs used in coloproctology	20	9	2	19	7	-	19	6	2	16	8	5	13	7	5
16	Medicines used in poisoning and intoxication	2	4	7	4	5	7	-	2	1	-	3	1	-	3	-
17	Enterosorbent drugs	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	3	-	-	4	-	-	4	-
18	Rehydrants for oral administration	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	2	-	-	2	-
19	Probiotics	-	-	-	2	-	-	10	1	-	11	-	-	11	-	-
20	Eubiotics	15	6	-	13	6	3	11	6	4	11	5	6	11	5	6
21	Hepatoprotectors	-	13	13	29	15	14	29	15	13	30	15	13	27	12	12
22	Choleretic drugs	5	7	10	5	7	10	3	7	6	3	6	7	3	6	5
23	Gallstone dissolving drugs	-	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	3	1	2	3	1	1
24	Anthelmintic and choleretic drugs	-	-	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
25	Other drugs for the treatment of biliary tract diseases	-	-	-	1	1	-	2	1	-	2	1	-	2	1	-
26	Medicines for the treatment of liver diseases	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
27	Medicines for the treatment of diseases of the liver and biliary tract	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	2	-	1	1	-
28	Appetite suppressants	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
29	Appetite enhancer	2	-	1	2	1	-	1	-	-	3	-	-	3	-	1
30	Other medicinal preparations for functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-
31	Medicines used to treat functional disorders of the gastrointestinal tract	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	1	-	-	-
32	Medicines for the treatment of functional intestinal diseases	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
33	Medicines for the treatment of pathologies of the gastrointestinal tract	7	-	-	8	-	-	6	-	-	3	-	-	3	-	-
34	Medicines for the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	-	-	3	-	-	-
35	Drugs for the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal tract and metabolism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
36	Drugs for the treatment of type 1 hereditary tyrosinemia	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
37	Other drugs affecting the digestive system and metabolism	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	-
38	Drugs for the treatment of primary biliary cirrhosis	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	1	-	-	-
	Total:	146	70	70	189	67	73	187	66	76	202	71	84	192	67	78

Table 4 presents an analysis of the assortment of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system according to pharmacological groups and international non-patented names, according to which, in 2019-2023, drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system were registered in the State Register by a total of 38 pharmacological groups. In 2019, 146 drugs from foreign countries were registered, and in 2023, 192 drugs were registered with an international non-patented name, and this rate increased by 31.5% in 5 years. In 2019, 70 medicines from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States were registered with an international non-patented name. In 2023, this indicator decreased by 4.29% to 67 drugs. In 2019, 70 drugs with international non-patented names were registered by local pharmaceutical enterprises, and in 2023, this figure increased by 11.42% and amounted to 78 drugs. It was also found that the registration rate in 2022-2023 was high during the 5-year period. According to the analysis by pharmacological groups, 30 hepatoprotective drugs of foreign producers were registered in 2022, 30 – in 2023, 17 drugs against gastrointestinal ulcer – in 2019, 20 – in 2023, 21 drugs against gastrointestinal ulcer (antacid) in 2020, 15 – in 2023, 20 drugs used in coloproctology in 2019, 13 – in 2023, 15 laxatives in 2019, 13 – in 2023. From the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States 13 hepatoprotective drugs were registered in 2019, 15 – in 2020, 9 drugs used in coloproctology – in 2019, 6 drugs – in 2021, 7 choleric drugs in 2019, 6 drugs – in 2023 with international unpatented names. From local pharmaceutical enterprises 12 laxative drugs were registered with international unpatented names in 2019, 15 – in 2021, 13 hepatoprotective drugs – in 2019, 14 – in 2020, 10 choleric drugs – in 2019, 5 drugs – in 2023.

Update index.

The index of renewal of drugs is an indicator of the development of the pharmaceutical industry, which is the development and improvement of the composition of the assortment and its compliance with the needs of specialists and patients.

In the study, we used the following formula to describe the I_o - update index of statistical indicators of the range of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system.

$$I_o = K_p / K_o \times 100 \%$$

Here, K_p – the number of international non-patented names (the number of drugs with international non-patented names registered for the first time in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2023);

K_o – the total number (the total number of drugs with international non-patented names according to the current register) [12].

The update of the assortment of drugs by the segment of the pharmaceutical market was determined for the period from 2019 to 2023 (by the year of registration in the Republic of Uzbekistan).

According to the calculation results, updating the range of medicines produced by foreign countries

$$I_o = 46 / 192 * 100 = 23,96 \%$$

Update of the range of medicines produced by local pharmaceutical enterprises

$$\text{And there is } I_o = 8 / 78 * 100 = 10,25 \%$$

There was almost no update of the range of medicines produced from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States.

Conclusions.

1. According to the results of the analysis of the range of drugs, the number of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of gastrointestinal system produced by foreign countries, countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States and local pharmaceutical enterprises entered into the State Register in 2019-2023 was recorded in high quantities in 2022, and it was found that a relatively large number (48.8 - 58.8%) of foreign states was registered.

2. India, Turkey, Germany from foreign countries in the analysis of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system registered in the state register of drugs, medical products and medical equipment approved for use in medical practice; from the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, it was scientifically determined that the rate of registration of international non-patented names and trade names from the countries of Russia, Ukraine and the Republic of Belarus is relatively high.

3. As a result of the analysis of international non-patented names of drugs used in the treatment of diseases of the gastrointestinal system by pharmacotherapeutic groups, drugs against gastrointestinal ulcers, drugs used in coloproctology, laxatives from drugs produced by foreign countries, countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States and local pharmaceutical enterprises, medicines and eubiotics play an important role.

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